

STARCH/BNC COMPOSITE FILMS ENRICHED WITH ANTHOCYANINS: SURFACE, WATER VAPOR PERMEABILITY AND COLORIMETRIC PROPERTIES

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Abstract: *In this research, colorimetric pH indicators based on biomaterials were produced. Potato, maize and wheat starch with the addition of bacterial nanocellulose were used as polymeric matrices for the production of indicators. Bacterial nanocellulose and natural pigments, anthocyanins extracted from red cabbage leaves, were added to film-forming solutions. Anthocyanins are water-soluble color pigments that are known for their color sensitivity to different pH values. This property is of great importance for the production of pH indicators, as food spoilage is often associated with changes in the natural pH value of fresh food, which can be detected on the food surface or in the packaging atmosphere. By using pH indicators, these changes can be easily monitored and visually detected. In this study, pH indicators were produced and their surface properties, water vapour permeability, transmission density and colorimetric properties of films immersed in different pH buffers were observed. The results have shown that different starch types and different amounts of bacterial nanocellulose lead to different surface and water vapor permeability properties as well as different colorimetric responses in an atmosphere with variable pH.*

Keywords: smart packaging, colorimetric indicators, biodegradable composite films

1 INTRODUCTION

The growing demand for food safety and extended shelf life has accelerated the development of smart packaging technologies. One of the most interesting innovations in this area is the integration of chromogenic indicators, materials that change color in response to certain stimuli, into packaging systems. Chromogenic indicators serve as visual sensors that provide real-time and non-destructive information about the condition of the packaged product or its storage. Among the different types of chromogenic indicators, pH-sensitive indicators are particularly effective for monitoring the freshness of perishable foods such as fish, meat and dairy products (Brockgreitens & Abbas, 2016; Thirupathi Vasuki et al., 2023). As microbial activity increases during spoilage, it often leads to the release of basic compounds such as ammonia or amines, resulting in a measurable shift in pH. PH indicators incorporated into the packaging can visibly change color in response to these chemical changes and thus serve as freshness indicators without having to open the packaging. One promising system for this application is composite films made from starch and bacterial nanocellulose (BNC), which are

enriched with anthocyanins. Starch is a natural, biodegradable polymer with good film-forming properties, while BNC, which is produced by certain bacterial strains, has excellent mechanical strength and barrier properties. In combination, these biopolymers form a bio-based matrix that can be used to produce a pH indicator. Anthocyanins, naturally occurring pigments found in fruits such as red cabbage, blueberries and blackberries, are known for their pH-sensitive chromogenic properties. When incorporated into starch/BNC films, anthocyanins enable the production of bio-based, colorimetric indicators that can visually indicate changes in pH and therefore food spoilage. Produced indicators can change color over a wide pH range, typically from red in an acidic environment to green or yellow in an alkaline environment and are therefore very effective for monitoring food freshness.

In this research, potato, maize and wheat starch were used as polymeric matrices to produce pH indicators. Anthocyanins were extracted from red cabbage and different amounts of BNC were added to film-forming solutions. The influence of BNC on the surface properties, water vapour permeability, transmission density and colorimetric properties of films was observed.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Preparation of the samples

Three types of starch were used for the production of pH indicators: potato starch (PS) (extra pure, CAS: 9005-25-8), maize starch (MS) (extra pure, CAS: 9005-25-8) and wheat starch (WS) (extra pure, CAS: 9005-25-8). Bacterial nanocellulose was prepared from the cellulose-rich biofilm formed after acetic acid fermentation of apple juice according to the previously published method (Mahović Poljaček et al., 2024). The prepared BNC was obtained in a suspension containing 2 % of the dry mass of the BNC (according to ISO 638-2:2022). The anthocyanins were extracted from red cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* L.). The extraction method and the calculation of the total content of monomeric anthocyanin pigments in red cabbage were carried out according to the previously published procedure (Mahović Poljaček et al., 2024).

The concentration of anthocyanins added to the film-forming solutions was 12 % (v/v) for the PS film solution, 14 % (v/v) for the MS film solution and 12 % (v/v) for the WS film solution. The films were prepared by dissolving starch in distilled water along with varying amounts of bacterial nanocellulose (BNC) (0 %, 30 % and 60 % (v/v)). This mixture was then placed on a temperature-controlled hotplate (Tehtnica, Rotamix 550 MMH, Slovenia) while stirring with a DLS Digital Overhead Stirrer (Velp Scientifica Srl, Italy). Glacial acetic acid (CAS: 64-19-7) (1 % v/v) was added to the film-forming solution under stirring at a concentration of 5 % (v/v) for PS-based films, 3 % (v/v) for MS-based films and 5 % (v/v) for WS-based films. Glycerol (purity 99.5 %, CAS: 56-81-5) was added to the potato, maize and wheat solutions at a concentration of 20 % (v/v), 15 % (v/v) and 20 % (v/v), respectively. After mixing for about 30 minutes, the film-forming solutions of a certain volume were poured into Petri dishes to obtain a constant film thickness, dried and stored for ten days in a ventilated climate chamber at 23 °C and 50 % relative humidity (RH). Depending on the type of starch used and the BNC concentration added, the films were labelled PS, MS or WS, i.e. 0BNC for films without BNC and 30BNC or 60BNC for films with different BNC concentrations.

2.2 Measurement and analysis methods

The optical density of the produced pH indicators was measured with the film transmission densitometer (Techkon Dens, TECHKON GmbH, Germany) to determine the influence of different starch types and different BNC concentrations on the film transparency. The colorimetric measurements of dried films and films immersed in different buffers were carried out with the Techkon SpectroDens (Techkon GmbH, Germany) with a D50 illuminant and a viewing angle of 2° using the M1 filter. The CIE L*a*b* values were calculated and the relative CIE L*a*b* values were displayed with paper as the white point. The results presented are the average values of ten measurements. The

contact angles of water on the prepared films were measured using a DataPhysics OCA 30 goniometer (DataPhysics Instruments GmbH, Filderstadt, Germany) using a sessile drop method with a drop volume of 1 μl . Ten measurements were taken on each film sample. Due to the rapid absorption of water on some films, the contact angles were recorded one second after contact of the water with the solid phase. It was measured to determine the wettability of pH indicators, which is important for understanding and controlling their surface properties. The calculation of water vapour transmission rate (WVTR) was determined according to the principles of ISO 2528:2018 and ASTM E96 at 23 °C and 50 % relative humidity. The gravimetric method was used and the WVTR values were calculated from the slope of weight change versus time (Song et al., 2014). This was used to evaluate the influence of the addition of BNC to the film-forming solution on the water vapor transmission rate.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Optical properties of dry films

Figure 1 shows the results of the lightness and optical transmission density of the dry film samples. The results of the relative lightness differ depending on the type of the starch and due to the addition of BNC. It lies between 57 (measured on WS_60BNC) and 77 (measured on PS_20BNC) units. The films containing BNC generally show a slight increase in lightness values compared to the films without BNC. The reason for this is probably the BNC itself, as it is not optically transparent but has a slightly yellowish color. An exception is the WS_60BNC sample, which has the lowest lightness value, which is probably due to the uneven homogenisation process of the components. It can also be seen that the type of thickness has a minor influence on the optical transmission density of the films produced. In general, films based on potato and maize starch had a higher optical density than films based on wheat starch. It should be noted that the addition of BNC slightly increases the density of all samples, which is probably due to its own colouring (BNC has a slightly yellowish color).

Figure 1: Optical density and lightness of the starch-based films

3.2 Contact angle of water

The water contact angle is useful for characterizing the surface properties of starch-based films with BNC by evaluating their hydrophilicity when using different starch types. Figure 2 displays the water contact angles of films made from various starches and different concentrations of BNC.

Figure 2: Contact angle of water on starch-based films with different BNC portions

The addition of BNC to the film compositions generally increased the water contact angle, with a more pronounced effect observed in films based on potato starch and maize starch. Although cellulose is made up of β -D-glucopyranose units that contribute to its hydrophilic nature, the electrostatic interactions and hydrogen bonding between BNC and starch can enhance the hydrophobicity of the surface (Lavrič et al., 2021; Bangar & Whiteside, 2021). The slightly different effects of BNC addition on the water contact angle of films made from wheat starch may be attributed to structural differences compared to maize starch and potato starch, such as the size of the starch molecules and the amylose content (Żołek-Tryznowska & Kałuża, 2021).

3.3 Water vapour transmission rate

The WVTR values of the starch-based films without and with the addition of BNC are listed in Table 1. The WVTR test was carried out at 23 °C and 50 % RH. For potato-based films, it was not possible to measure the WVTR as the samples were too fragile, so this test was not performed. The results showed that wheat starch-based films had higher total WVTR than maize starch-based films. The measured WVTR values were 23.84 and 20.88 g m⁻² h⁻¹ for samples without BNC, maize and wheat, respectively. In both cases, the addition of BNC resulted in a small increase in WVTR, indicating a negative effect on water vapour permeability. Although it was expected that the addition of BNC would decrease WVTR, it appears that BNC causes an increase in WVTR. According to Gitari et al. (2019), a high BNC content in nanocomposite films could be the reason for the decrease in WVTR. BNC consists of a network of fibres that make it porous and have a large surface area. With a high BNC content in the starch-based films, the fibres begin to form agglomerations (Sardjono et al., 2025; Zong et al., 2014), which can promote the transport of water vapour through the produced films. It can be said that a lower amount of BNC should be further tested in order to obtain a lower WVTR property, as a high fibre content can deteriorate the barrier properties.

Table 1: Water vapor transmission rate (WVTR)

WVTR (g m ⁻² h ⁻¹)	MS_0BNC	MS_60BNC	WS_0BNC	WS_60BNC
	23.84	27.01	20.88	21.80

3.4 Colorimetric analysis

Figures 3.a-3.c present the changes in CIE a* and b* values of the produced films. To highlight and compare the trends in CIE a*/b* shifts across different pH environments, a B-spline trendline was added to the plots.

Figure 3: CIE a^*/b^* diagrams for films at different pH values: a) PS-based, b) MS-based, c) WS-based

The pH-dependent variations in a^* and b^* values of the films were influenced by both the type of starch used and the concentration of BNC. The trendlines for the CIE a^*/b^* data points for potato and wheat starch showed a noticeable shift towards $+b^*$ values as the concentration of BNC increased in mildly acidic, neutral, and mildly basic environments. This shift can be attributed to the hue of the BNC used and its interaction with anthocyanins, affecting their structural changes. As the pH changed, the color of the films transitioned from pink hues at acidic pH to nearly colourless hues at neutral pH, and finally to green-yellow hues at alkaline pH. While the addition of BNC did not significantly impact the $+a^*/-a^*$ color shift, the type of starch did have a notable effect. Films based on maize starch exhibited the widest range of a^* values when immersed in buffers with varying pH levels, whereas films based on wheat starch showed the narrowest range on the a^* axis. This suggests that the type of starch affects the degree of color change in the films. Furthermore, the changes in a^*/b^* plots indicate that BNC can stabilize anthocyanins when exposed to different pH levels, which is consistent with previous research (Mahović Poljaček et al., 2024). BNC creates a network that protects anthocyanins from their breakdown, which is visible in the lower b^* value (i.e., yellow hues) at highly alkaline pH for the samples with BNC, pointing to the decreased presence of the chalcone structure (Ohno et al., 2021). However, the type of starch used can influence the colorimetric changes observed in the films when they are exposed to varying pH environments. Therefore, careful selection of the starch for film production is

essential to optimize both the functional properties (such as barrier and mechanical properties) and the colorimetric response of the produced films.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, pH-sensitive starch-based films containing bacterial nanocellulose (BNC) and anthocyanins from red cabbage were used to observe their potential for the production of pH indicators. Potato, maize and wheat starch were used as polymeric matrices. Different amounts of BNC were added to the film-forming solutions to observe their influence on the surface properties, water vapour permeability, transmission density and colorimetric properties of the produced films. The results showed that the interactions between the main components of the films and the resulting property changes were significantly influenced by the BNC concentration and the type of starch. It was found that films containing BNC generally showed a slight increase in lightness values compared to the films without BNC and a slight decrease in transmission density. The addition of BNC to the film compositions generally increased the water contact angle, with a stronger effect observed in films based on potato and maize starch based films. The results showed that wheat starch-based films had an overall higher WVTR than maize starch-based films and that the high BNC content in the nanocomposite films could cause the decrease in the WVTR property. The results of the colorimetric measurement showed that maize starch-based films exhibited the widest range of changes in the red and green color directions when immersed in buffers with different pH values, while wheat starch-based films exhibited the narrowest range within the same color range. This indicates that the type of starch has a significant influence on the extent of color change in the films.

The results obtained in this study show that the addition of a small amount of BNC to starch-based films, particularly when MS and WS films are involved, provides a potentially significant advantage for the production of pH indicators for smart packaging applications.

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